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Spectroscopic on-line sensing for monitoring and control of microalgal cultivations

L. Porras-Reyes¹⁾, M. Rausch¹⁾, Dr. I. Havlik¹⁾, Dr. S. Beutel¹⁾ (E-Mail: Beutel@iftc.uni-hannover.de)¹⁾Leibniz University of Hannover, Institute of Technical Chemistry, Callinstr. 3–5, 30167 Hannover, Germany

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Microalgae are well-known photosynthetic microbes used as cell factories to produce relevant biotechnological compounds. However, industrial-scale production of microalgae is still at an early stage of development and the economically viable support of the sustainable large-scale production of microalgae at the present state of technology is a challenge.

One important bottleneck in this support is the lack of suitable on-line sensors for the reliable monitoring of biological

parameters, mostly concentration of intracellular components, in microalgae bioprocesses. The application of software sensors using physical signal inputs of multiple sensors could complement the on-line monitoring as it allows the estimation of the desired biological process variables in real or almost-real time which are often hidden in the spectroscopic data.

Sensing elements for microalgal cultivation monitoring are presented for gather-

ing spectroscopic data from UV-VIS-IR measurements. The respective self-constructed sensors are placed in a bypass using flow-cells prototypes, designed by additive manufacturing/rapid prototyping. Their signal outputs are processed by a combination of a chemometric model/artificial neural network to estimate the biomass concentration and pigment contents of the microalgal culture.

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deepLAB: A new concept for parallel operated milliliter-scale stirred-tank bioreactors using offgas technology for model-based process optimization

J. Sturm¹⁾ (E-Mail: Jonathan.sturm@agbioprozesstechnik.de), R. Janetzky¹⁾, Dr. F. Eiden¹⁾¹⁾Westfälische Hochschule, AG BioProzessTechnik, August-Schmidt-Ring 10, 45665 Recklinghausen, Germany

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Controlled parallel bioreactor systems allow fed-batch operation at early stages of process development. Parallel fed-batch operation is achieved with an intermittent feeding and offgas-control system for up to 16 bioreactors operated in parallel on a scale of 50 mL. Examples of the scale-up and scale-down of offgas-controlled microbial fed-batch processes demonstrate that controlled parallel reactor systems can result in more effective bioprocess development.

A comprehensive platform was developed, consisting of off-gas sensor (in 3D printed case) and an external micropump

coupled with a model-based operation software framework to increase the efficiency in high-throughput bioprocess development. Using macro-kinetic growth models, the platform has been successfully used for the development of scale-down fed-batch cultivations in parallel mini-bioreactor systems. However, it has also been shown that parametric uncertainties in the models can significantly affect the prediction accuracy and thus the reliability of optimized cultivation strategies. To tackle this issue, a multistage model predictive control (MPC) strategy was implemented to fulfill the experimental objectives under

Figure. Eight off-gas sensors in 3D printed cases on a stirring plate.

tight constraints despite the uncertainty in the parameters and the measurements.

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deepPilot: Automated robust process control based on a data-driven model

F. Dymek¹⁾, J. Sturm¹⁾ (E-Mail: Jonathan.sturm@agbioprozesstechnik.de), Dr. F. Eiden¹⁾¹⁾Westfälische Hochschule, AG BioProzessTechnik, August-Schmidt-Ring 10, 45665 Recklinghausen, Germany

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